

ADVANCED SMC-PROCESSING IN COMBINATION WITH TEXTILE REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In Europe, Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) has high market relevance in the field of glass fiber reinforced polymer composites with a market share of almost 20 % in terms of mass. The material is especially popular in automotive industry since it provides a thermal expansion coefficient similar to steel and special grades allow Class-A surface quality. On the other hand the mechanical properties of SMC components are often limited by the type of fiber and fiber length, which impedes the usage e.g. for structural applications. Within the project “Preform-SMC” the standard SMC material (chopped long fibers) is synergistically combined with the preform technology (textiles) in order to improve the overall performance of components. Therefore, dry textile preforms were integrated in the standardized SMC process, by placing them in the mold together with the SMC semi-finished product. The aim of this study was to investigate the impregnation of the dry preforms with the resin of the SMC semi-finished product during the press process. The studies revealed that the quality of the impregnation of the preform is mainly determined by the density of the SMC semi-finished product and the layer structure of the reinforcing fibers. Locally implemented reinforcing textiles improve the mechanical properties. Depending on the fiber type and the layer structure e.g. Young’s Modulus could be doubled, tensile strength could be quadrupled.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to steadily increasing energy prices, global warming and increasing scarcity of resources, composite materials are gaining importance. Based on their specific advantages, parts can be individually designed based on specific requirements. Especially high-performance composites, which are commonly based on carbon fibers with long- and continuous filament reinforcements, provide a tremendous lightweight potential resulting from the pronounced anisotropic material behavior. Unfavorable for the use of such parts is the very high price of the carbon reinforcement fibers, which is at about 20-30 € / kg [1]. Additional costs for further processing from the filament fibers to non-crimp or woven fabrics limit the cost-efficient application, for example in the aerospace and automotive sector.

Contrary to continuous reinforced composites, SMC provides the opportunity of producing glass fiber reinforced parts by compression molding process at advantageous prices. With this process the mass production of parts with near-net-shape geometry and constant wall thickness as well as constant quality is possible. Therefore, SMC has high market relevance and is well established, as it – depending on the additives – can be used for numerous applications (e.g. in the automotive industry, the transport sector, or for cable cabinets). However, there are some limitations of use due to the length of reinforcement fibers, which are normally cut to a length of 0.5 or 1 inch.

SMC semi-finished product consists of a highly filled resin like e.g. unsaturated polyester resin or vinyl ester resin and glass fibers. To produce the SMC semi-finished product, a resin film of homogeneous thickness is applied to a styrene-proof carrier foil. On top of this resin film, glass fibers, which are evenly distributed and cut by a cutting unit, are arranged. A second carrier foil with a second resin film is placed on top of the glass fibers in order to achieve a symmetrical layer structure. Afterwards, this layer structure passes a tumbling area where the fibers are impregnated by SMC resin paste. Finally, the semi-finished SMC product is rolled up and sealed in a styrene-proof bag. After

production, the material has to mature about 14 days. Within this time the viscosity rises and the material gets more and more homogeneous.

To expand the characteristic profile of SMC parts and their application field, e.g. as structural parts, within the project ‘‘Preform-SMC’’ a new and innovative composite material has been investigated. The hybrid material results from a combination of SMC and preforming technology. During a compression molding process, a dry reinforcement structure should be completely in-situ impregnated by SMC resin paste. Due to the implementation of continuous reinforcement fibers into SMC parts, the structure properties should be improved.

A further advantage of the new material is the reduction of the wall thickness and thus a reduction of the weight of SMC parts. Based on this process, the advantages of the parallel regulated press process (e.g. short cycle times, die-cut and near-net components) and the advantages of preforming technology (e.g. fiber-orientation along load paths, improvement of structural mechanics, locally adapted fiber volume content) are combined to enable new application fields for SMC parts, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Project idea Preform-SMC

The impregnation of the dry inserted reinforcement textile by the SMC resin paste mainly takes place in through-the-thickness direction of the textile. The impregnability of the preform depends amongst others on the out-of-plane permeability of the textile, which is determined by its architecture (e.g. stitching parameters) [3]. Also the chemical composition of the SMC resin paste (resin type, fiber- or filler content, additives, etc.) plays a crucial role in the impregnation process and end part quality. If the SMC resin paste flows in the through-the-thickness direction of the reinforcing textile, the textile acts like a sieve and filters out the filling material of the SMC. This filtering process seals the flow paths within the textile and thus prevents matrix from flowing through the textile, so that there are non-impregnated areas in reinforcement textile.

To achieve a well impregnation of the reinforcement textile, the knowledge of the out-of-plane permeability and the selection of an appropriate SMC-semi finished product with low adapted filler content are indispensable.

2 MATERIALS

Three standard SMC semi-finished products (Table 1), and two non-crimp fabric reinforcement textiles (Table 2), are considered within the study. The SMC semi-finished products differ only in the filler content which leads to different material densities. Commonly, SMC semi-finished product consists of thermoset resin system (15 %), based on unsaturated polyester resins, glass fibers (30 %), thermoplastic resin (9 %), filling material (42 %), and miscellaneous fillers (4 %), see Figure 2 [4].

Engineering constant		SMC A	SMC B	SMC C
<i>Grammage</i>	[g/m ²]	3600	3600	3600
<i>Fiber content by weight</i>	[%]	30	30	30
<i>Density</i>	[g/cm ³]	1.73	1.80	1.88
<i>Young's modulus</i>	[GPa]	10.0	11.0	11.5

Table 1: SMC materials considered in the study

Figure 2: Typical ingredients of SMC semi-finished product [4]

As reinforcing textiles, different non-crimp fabrics (NCF) and fabrics were previously tested [3]. For this study suitable reinforcing textiles with same fiber orientation, but differing in type of fiber, were used, see Table 2.

Engineering constant	Reinforcement textile 1	Reinforcement textile 2
<i>Fiber type</i>	GF	CF
<i>Structure</i>	+/-45°NCF	+/-45°NCF
<i>Grammage</i> [g/m ²]	620	540

Table 2: Reinforcement textiles considered in this study

3 METHODS

3.1 Permeability measurement

The out-of-plane permeability was measured with a re-engineered measuring cell based on the cell of Stöven et al [2], see Figure 3. The measuring cell uses ultrasonic technology to detect the progress of the flow front of measurement fluid which is point-injected into the textile lay-up.

Figure 3: Cross-section of the out-of-plane measuring cell [2]

The time-of-flight of the ultrasound signal in the unsaturated and saturated part of the preform is different. Due to this, it is possible to track the progress of the flow front while the measurement fluid infiltrates the fiber stack. The fiber volume content of the sample can be calculated by the number of layers, the area weight, and the density of the fibers. The cavity height is constant for all measurements. As measurement fluid rapeseed oil with known viscosity was used [3]. The through-the-thickness permeability (K) can be calculated using the Darcy equation (1), which correlates the permeability with the viscosity of the impregnation fluid (η), the volume-averaged flow velocity (ν), and the known pressure gradient in flow direction ($\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta r}$).

$$v = -\frac{K}{\eta} \cdot \frac{dP}{dr} \quad (1)$$

3.2 Press rheometry

To characterize the viscosity and the flow behavior of different SMC semi-finished products which only differ in density (see Table 1), press rheometry measurements were carried out on the IVW press rheometer, see Figure 4. For these trials, the material was first cut into circular shaped specimen with a diameter of 350 mm and stacked between two flat circular plates which were mounted on the press. The diameter of the used pressing plates is 344 mm and both the top and bottom plates could be heated to the required processing temperature. The press was closed with a constant closing speed of 1.5 mm/s. Due to the known constant pressing area, the pressing force could then be used to calculate a compression stress and a compaction in thickness-direction of the stack [5].

Figure 4: IVW press rheometer in an 800 tons parallel regulated press

3.3 Compression molding process

SMC semi-finished product is processed by compression molding on parallel controlled press on tools with sealing edges to partly high complex and relatively large parts (e.g. interior trim of local transport system). The prepreg material is cut with CNC-controlled cutting machines to the required dimensions and stacked to packages that are exactly positioned in the mold. The temperature of the mold is at about 130 - 160 °C, the occupancy is usually between 40 - 60 % and normally the pressure inside the tool is between 50 - 120 bars [5]. When closing the tool, the package is compressed and heated up. The increase of the temperature leads to decrease of the SMC resin paste viscosity. This change of viscosity enables the SMC material to flow and to fill-up the mold completely. The chopped short fibers with a length of 0.5 to 1.0 inch are carried along and distributed among the complete tool by the flow of the SMC resin paste. The temperature of the tool also initiates curing of the SMC material and enables thermoplastic shrinkage compensation. After the part is cured, it can be removed from the tool and reworked. The difference between the test series is the type of SMC prepreg material, number of reinforcement layers (one or two), and the layer structure.

3.3.1 Preliminary impregnation tests in laboratory scale

To investigate the influence of the different filler contents on the impregnation quality, preliminary test series with the different SMC prepreg materials (Table 1) were performed. The press conditions and the reinforcement textiles were equal for all tests. For these trials a Satim laboratory press with a maximum press force of 1200 kN was used. The dimensions of the tool are 380 x 460 mm². Both the upper tool and the lower tool were heated to the required tooling temperature of at about 150°C. On one layer of reinforcement textile, which was placed centrally on the bottom of the mold, a layer SMC-sheet was placed. This sequence prevented a premature curing of the SMC sheets, caused by the heat of the surface of the tool. After that, the press was closed with a maximum pressure inside the cavity of 60 bars with a holding time between 180 and 240 seconds.

Figure 5: Insertion of reinforcement textile and SMC sheet

3.3.2 Impregnation trials with flat plate tool in quasi-industrial scale

In a next step, impregnation trials were carried out on a parallel regulated Dieffenbacher press with a maximum press force of 8000 kN. The dimensions of the tool are 543 x 543 mm², see Figure 6. As in the previous tests one layer of reinforcement textile was placed centrally on the bottom of the mold; on top of this layer SMC sheets were laid.

The main challenge of these trials is the impregnation of the dry inserted reinforcement textiles within a standardized pressing process without warping or breaking the textile inside the mold.

Further targets of the trials are a completely filled tool whereby the thickness of the plate should be 2 – 3 mm, regarding valid test specifications [6, 7]. Subsequently, test specimens were cut for mechanical and rheological characterization.

Figure 6: 8000 kN parallel controlled component press with installed sealing edge tool

3.3.3 Impregnation trials with a part tool

Based on the preliminary impregnation tests and the results with the flat plate tool, impregnation tests on a curved tool with ribs, with the dimension 445 x 300 mm², see Figure 7, were carried out. Within this tool, different impregnation studies were performed. At first, the impregnation of a top layer was investigated. The second study investigated the impregnation of reinforcement textile layers, centred in the thickness of the component. Therefore, a five-layer (SMC-textile-SMC-textile-SMC) setup was used. To prevent the flow of the reinforcement textile into the rib, small sheets of SMC prepreg material were laid into the rib cavity first, see Figure 7, left. Figure 7 right shows the complexly curved part.

Figure 7: Complexly curved tool, including ribs (left), demonstration part (right)

3.4 Light Microscopy

The impregnation quality of the different reinforced SMC samples was analyzed using a light microscope to determine the void content in the finished part. Therefore, small pieces (20 x 20 mm²) of the different samples were embedded into EP-resin. After the resin cured, the samples were grounded and polished. With a magnification of 25 till 500, pictures of the samples were made to investigate void content inside reinforcement textile.

3.5 Mechanical properties

Tensile properties were measured according to DIN EN ISO 527-4 on a Zwick universal testing machine, type 1485. Specimen size was 250 mm x 25 mm, type 2.

Bending properties were measured according to DIN 14125 on a Zwick universal testing machine. Specimen size was 64 mm x 15 mm, class of materials three.

Charpy impact resistance was tested according to DIN EN ISO 179 with unnotched specimens, type 2. Specimen size was 80 mm x 15 mm, span $L = 20 \times$ thickness of the specimen.

For a statistical basis, at least seven tests were made for every test configuration.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results of permeability measurement

In different previous works the out-of-plane permeability of more than 150 different reinforcing materials including glass-fiber-, carbon fiber-(non) crimp fabrics and textiles was determined. These measurements showed that on the one hand the out-of-plane permeability of $\pm 45^\circ$ -NCF is much higher than of $0/90^\circ$ -NCF. This is based on the stitching seam through the thickness of the single layers. This stitching seam acts like a flow channel and increases the out-of-plane permeability [8]. On the other hand the out-of-plane permeability of NCFs is much higher than of fabrics.

Based on these results a $\pm 45^\circ$ -CF-NCF and a $\pm 45^\circ$ -GF-NCF were chosen for further analyses, see Table 2.

4.2 Results of material characterization using Press Rheometry

Figure 8 shows the results of the press rheometry. Hereby the graph, which demonstrates the press force over the press time, is clearly split into three sections. At the first section (0-10 s) the press force rises and induces both a compaction of the sample and a full-area contact of the outer layers of the stack with the heated surface of the press rheometer. In the second area can be observed that the warming up of the materials decreases viscosity and the material starts to flow (10-30 s). Above 30 s, the curing reaction takes place increasing again the viscosity of the SMC. This leads to a higher needed press force while the material flows and fills-up the mold completely. It can be clearly seen that the SMC material with the highest filler content (SMC type C, section three, left line) requires the highest press forces to flow into the mold.

Figure 8: Results of press rheometry

4.3 Results of preliminary impregnation tests

In a further step a comprehensive study was performed to characterize the impregnation quality of the selected dry textiles with the different standard SMC prepreg materials, which differ only in filler content and density. These tests showed that the filler content has a strong influence on the impregnation quality, Table 3. Hereby, dark sections show unimpregnated reinforcement textiles and light areas show impregnated areas. To enable a better view on the light optical microscope, images are colored in green.

This overview shows that with exactly same press conditions, the SMC prepreg material with the lowest filler content leads to the best impregnation results.

Uninfiltrated reinforcement textile	Processing parameter: 148 °C, 50 bar, 180 sec		
	SMC 1	SMC 2	SMC 3
	Lowest filler content, lowest density $\rho=1,6 \text{ g/cm}^3$	Middle filler content, middle density $\rho=1,7 \text{ g/cm}^3$	Highest filler content, highest density $\rho=1,8 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Table 3: Impregnation results of different SMC prepreg materials

Due to an optimized combination of suitable reinforcement textiles ($\pm 45^\circ$ GF-or CF-NCF) with a high out-of-plane permeability and an SMC semi-finished product (Table 1, material A) with a relatively low processing viscosity of the resin paste and an optimized press process, a well impregnation of the textiles can be achieved. This was proven by light microscopy analysis, see chapter 4.4.

4.4 Results of impregnation trials (flat plate)

Plates with different layer structures, reinforcing textiles, SMC semi-finished products and different press cycles were manufactured. In this case the impregnation studies were carried out with three different SMC semi-finished products, two different reinforcing textiles and different layer structures, see Table 2. The sample structure is systematically shown with solid lines for SMC sheets and dotted lines for layers of reinforcing textile.

Sample Number	SMC semi-finished material	Reinforcing textile	Tool assignment (SMC) [%]	Tool assignment (reinforcing textile) [%]	Pressure inside the mold [bars]	Sample structure
1	A	1	approx. 100	approx. 100	30	=====
2	A	1	approx. 100	approx. 100	150	=====
3	C	1	approx. 100	approx. 100	150	=====
4	A	1	approx. 60	approx. 100	150	=====
5	A	2	approx. 100	approx. 100	150	=====
6	A	2	approx. 60	approx. 100	150	=====

Table 4: Composition of the manufactured composite plates

Within the first press trials the optimum quantity of SMC semi-finished product to fill the mold completely was investigated. The parameters for these trials were: 30 bars pressure inside the mold, tool assignment nearly 100 %, tool temperature at about 140°C, hold time 240 s. To fill the mold completely, approximately 1080 g semi-finished product were needed. Thereafter, the pressure inside the tool was gradually increased from 30 to 150 bars, in order to obtain a satisfactory impregnation of the reinforcement textile. With increasing pressure inside the mold, the impregnation quality of the reinforcement textile improved, so 150 bars pressure were used for the subsequent trials.

In a further optimization step to improve the impregnation the reinforcement textile and the SMC stack were placed in the heated tool and the press was closed for about 20 seconds with minimum press force before applying the end pressure of 150 bars. The raise of temperature inside the SMC semi-finished product decreased its viscosity and improved the impregnation of reinforcement textile by SMC resin-paste.

In a further step tool assignment of reinforcement textile and SMC semi-finished product was reduced to approximately 65 % to see the influence of the flow of material inside the tool to the reinforcement textile, see Figure 9. On top of the GF-NCF (540 x 355 mm²) one respectively two layers of SMC semi-finished product were placed and the mold was closed. After the optimized press cycle, the GF-NCF was completely impregnated and the mold was completely filled. Although the tool assignment was reduced, the dimensions of the reinforcement textile remained almost unchanged, see Figure 10. This is based on the symmetrical flow of the SMC semi-finished product in only one direction of the tool. If the SMC semi-finished product does not flow symmetrical in the mold, it drags the reinforcement material along the flow front. To prevent this, fixation e.g. clamps for the reinforcement textiles during press cycle is needed.

Figure 9: Tool assignment of glass fiber (approx. 65 %)

Figure 10: Reinforcement textile after press process (approx. 65 %)

The studies showed that the best impregnation results were achieved with a SMC semi-finished product with low density (material A), GF-NCF with a layer structure of $\pm 45^\circ$ (reinforcing textile 1), and a high pressure inside the mold (150 bars). The trials also showed that SMC resin-paste could not flow through several textile layers and impregnate more than one layer of reinforcement textile.

4.5 Results of light microscopy analysis

The impregnation quality of the pressed parts was investigated by light microscopy. The micro section pictures **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** and **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** show two specimen which were processed under exactly the same process conditions (tool temperature 140°C, press force 4500 kN, holding time 240 s) while the same type of reinforcement textile ($\pm 45^\circ$ GF-NCF) was impregnated. The only difference is the density of the SMC semi-finished product. The impregnation direction of the dry inserted reinforcement textile was from the top to the bottom. The quality of the impregnation of the reinforcement textile was determined by the void content and showed significant differences. Moreover the determination of the void content demonstrated that a highly filled SMC semi-finished product leads to three times as many voids (black spots) (9 %, Figure 12**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) as a low filled SMC (3 %, Figure 11).

Figure 11: Microsection of test specimen with low filled SMC semi-finished product

Figure 12: Microsection of test specimen with highly filled SMC semi-finished product

A verification of the impregnation quality of the textile reinforcement fibers with micro section showed the possibility to impregnate the reinforcement textile almost completely by SMC resin.

4.6 Results of impregnation trials with a part tool

Based on the results of the tests with the flat plate tool, impregnation tests with a part tool were carried out. The main targets of these trials are a completely impregnated reinforcement textile and a completely filled tool, including ribs.

4.6.1 Impregnation of top layers

Similar to the flat plate tool, initially the mass required for a complete filling of the curved tool, including an integrated rib structure, was investigated. Thereafter, one layer of textile reinforcement and SMC sheets were inserted into the tool and first impregnation trials were carried out. The first trials applying SMC-sheets just on the top of the dry textile showed that neither the tool could be filled nor the dry reinforcement textile could be completely impregnated. With an optimized press cycle and an optimized mass of SMC semi-finished product the mold was almost completely filled and the top layer was better impregnated, see Table 5. In a further optimization step, a second sheet of SMC semi-finished product was placed on top of reinforcement textile. This sheet should impregnate the reinforcement textile on top and simultaneously provide a high surface quality. The study showed the feasibility of the impregnation of reinforcement textiles on curved shapes, simultaneously filling ribs of the part and accomplishing a good surface quality.

	First impregnation step	Second impregnation step	Third impregnation step
<i>Internal view</i>			
<i>External view</i>			
<i>Description</i>	Result of the first impregnation trials with a complexly curved tool	Optimized mounting of SMC semi-finished product in the mold	Optimized press process, completely filled and impregnated part

Table 5: Impregnation and tool filling results before and after optimization

4.6.2 Impregnation of layers in the middle of the part

Based on the knowledge of the impregnation of top layers trials with additional reinforcement layers were carried out. Tool assignment was at about 100 % by reinforcement fibers and 60 % by SMC semi-finished product. A five layer structure had to be processed (SMC-textile-SMC-textile-SMC). Figure 13 shows a sectional view of the five-layer component with a total length of at about 60 mm. For a better top view, the individual microsections are put together in one straight line. It is recognizable, that the distance over single reinforcement layers is nearly constant over the complete curved structure. In order to prevent that the reinforcement textile flows into the rib of the mold, SMC-sheets are inserted into the rib before the mold closes.

Figure 13: Sectional view of the curved component including the rib.

Micro sections show that it is possible to impregnate a reinforcement textile with a multilayer layer structure in a complexly curved tool and simultaneously obtaining a surface with high quality.

4.7 Results of mechanical properties

4.7.1 Tensile test

At first the unreinforced reference material (SMC type A) was tested. The results correspond to the data of the manufacturer. The test series differ on the type of reinforcement fiber, number of reinforcement layers (one or two), and the layer structure, see Table 4.

Figure 14 shows the results of Young's Modulus, with a fiber orientation parallel to load direction. A single-sided reinforcement of glass fibers at the outside of the specimen leads to an increasing of Young's Modulus of at about 45 %. A second layer of reinforcement at the other side increases the modulus to at about 55 %. The reinforcement on both sides of the sample with carbon fibers leads to an increase of at about 220 % of the unreinforced value. All reinforced samples had almost the same weight as the unreinforced samples. By inserting and infiltrating one respectively two layers of textile reinforcement, fiber mass content was increased by 36 % respectively 40 %. The thickness of the plates is limited by the press tool, and insofar there are textile reinforcement layers as covering layers, there is less unreinforced SMC resin paste in the rest of the cross section. Thereby, a higher fiber volume content is achieved.

Regarding tensile strength, see Figure 14, an increase of 300 % could be achieved by implementing reinforcement textile on one side of the specimen. Comparing the double sided reinforcement, there is no big difference between GF and CF, based on a worse impregnation of CF.

Figure 14: Young's modulus (left) and tensile strength (right) according to DIN EN ISO 527-4

4.7.2 Bending test

In previous tests, bending properties of unreinforced material were tested (SMC type A). The results corresponded almost to the data of the manufacturer.

Figure 15 shows the results of bending strength and flexural modulus. The reinforcing textile was placed on the bottom of the test sample where tensile load appears. A single sided reinforcement of glass fibers leads to an increase of at about 140 % regarding bending strength and at about 125 % regarding flexural modulus. The insertion of a second layer on the opposite top of the sample could not increase the bending strength. This could be explained as these fibers are loaded on pressure and not on tension. The replacement of GF- by CF reinforcement fibers on both sides of the sample did not increase bending strength, while flexural modulus could be increased for further 190 %. The increase of the bending strength is based on higher fiber volume content with simultaneous orientation of the reinforcing fibers in load path direction.

Figure 15: Bending strength (left) and flexural modulus (right) according to DIN EN ISO 14125

5 CONCLUSIONS

The project “Preform-SMC” proved the possibility to impregnate locally inserted dry textile reinforcement structures within a conventional SMC press process and conventional SMC semi-finished product. The combination of the textile reinforcement with a conventional short fiber SMC material enables the production of complex component geometries with increased mechanical properties. This is based on the higher fiber volume content and the possibility to align the reinforcement fibers along load paths.

Based on the improved mechanical properties, the wall thickness of the components as also the weight of the components can also be reduced. Another advantage of the increased properties is the possibility of tapping into new application fields, e.g. for structural applications.

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